

THE MAGNETIC CHAIN MATHEMATICAL MODELS OF A NEW ANGULAR DISPLACEMENT SENSOR WITH A VARIABLE ACTIVE AREA OF THE A MOVABLE CORE

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Abstract. The article develops mathematical models of the magnetic chain of new differential type angular displacement transformer converter with a variable active area of the movable core, in which the width of the movable ferromagnetic core is a function of the angular displacement of the converter. In this case, the magnetic chain of the converter, divided into three characteristic (before the mobile ferromagnetic core, ferromagnetic core and after the ferromagnetic core) sections, is considered as a magnetic chain with distributed parameters. It is established that when the magnetic resistance of the magnetic chain steel part is not taken into account, the working magnetic flux is a linear function of the angular displacement of the movable ferromagnetic core of the converter. The obtained mathematical models of the magnetic chain of the transformer converter of angular displacements in the form of analytical expressions of the magnetic flux in long ferromagnetic rods and the magnetic voltage between them for three characteristic sections allow to take into account the distribution of the parameters of the magnetic resistance of long ferromagnetic rods and the magnetic capacity of the air gap between them, as well as the magnetic capacity of the air gap between the rods and the movable ferromagnetic core.

Keywords: differential transformer converter, angular displacement, crescent-shaped open ring, magnetic chain, distributed parameter, linear magnetic resistance, linear magnetic capacitance, magnetic flux, magnetic voltage, linearity of flow distribution, magnetic flux propagation coefficient, characteristic sections of the magnetic chain.

Аннотация. Мақолада қўзгалувчан ферромагнит ўзагининг фаол юзаси ўзгарувчан, яъни қўзгалувчан ферромагнит ўзак эни ўзгартиргич бурчак силжиишларининг функцияси бўлган дифференциал русумли бурчак силжиишлари янги трансформатор ўзгартиргичи магнит занжирининг математик моделлари ишлаб чиқилган. Бунда ўзгартиргич магнит занжири учта (қўзгалувчан ферроматнит ўзаккача, ферроматнит ўзакда ва ферроматнит ўзакдан кейин) хос участкага ажратилган тақсимланган параметрли магнит занжири сифатида кўриб чиқилган. Магнит занжири нўлат қисмининг магнит қариилиги ҳисобга олинмаганида ишчи магнит оқими ўзгартиргич қўзгалувчан ферромагнит ўзаги бурчак силжиишининг чизиқли функцияси бўлиши аниқланган. Бурчак силжиишлари трансформатор ўзгартиргичи магнит занжирининг узун ферромагнит стерженларидаги магнит оқимлари ва улар орасидаги магнит кучланишининг аналитик ифодалари кўринишида уч хил характерли участкалари учун ҳосил қилинган математик моделлари узун ферромагнит стерженлар магнит қариилиги ва улар орасидаги ҳаво оралиги, шунингдек стерженлар ва қўзгалувчан ферромагнит ўзак орасидаги ҳаво оралиқлари магнит сизими параметрларининг тақсимланганлигини ҳисобга олиши имконини беради.

Калим сўзлар: дифференциал трансформатор ўзгартиргичи, бурчакли силжииш, ўроқ шаклидаги очиқ ҳалқа, магнит занжири, тақсимланган параметр, солиитирма магнит қариилиги, солиитирма магнит сизими, магнит оқими, магнит кучланиши, оқим тақсимланишининг чизиқлилиги, магнит оқимининг тарқалиши коэффициенти, магнит занжирнинг хос бўлаклари.

Аннотация. В статье разработаны математические модели магнитной цепи нового трансформаторного преобразователя угловых перемещений дифференциального типа с переменной активной площадью подвижного сердечника, в которой ширина подвижного ферромагнитного сердечника является функцией углового перемещения преобразователя. При этом магнитная цепь преобразователя, расчлененная на трех характерных (до подвижного ферромагнитного сердечника, ферромагнитного сердечника и после ферромагнитного сердечника) участков, рассматривается как магнитная цепь с распределенными параметрами. Установлено, что при неучете магнитного сопротивления стальной части магнитной цепи рабочий магнитный поток является линейной функцией углового перемещения подвижного ферромагнитного сердечника преобразователя. Полученные математические модели магнитной цепи трансформаторного преобразователя угловых перемещений в виде аналитических выражений магнитного потока в длинных ферромагнитных стержнях и магнитного напряжения между ними для трех характерных участков позволяет учитывать распределенность параметров магнитного сопротивления длинных ферромагнитных стержней и магнитной емкости воздушного зазора между ними, а также магнитной емкости воздушного зазора между стержнями и подвижным ферромагнитным сердечником.

Ключевые слова: дифференциальный трансформаторный преобразователь, угловое перемещение, серпообразное незамкнутое кольцо, магнитная цепь, распределенный параметр, погонное магнитное сопротивление, погонная магнитная емкость, магнитный поток, магнитное напряжение, линейность потокораспределения, коэффициент распространения магнитного потока, характерные участки магнитной цепи.

Introduction. Electromagnetic converters, in particular, transformer converters are widely used for obtaining reliable information about the angular movements of controlled objects in automatic control systems and management of various technological and production processes [1,2]. Compared with other types of angular displacement converters, they have high reliability and stable metrological characteristics in extreme operating conditions [3,4].

The transformer converter of angular displacements contains a fixed magnetic core made in the form of two crescent-shaped open rings 1 and 2 with a working area linearly varying in angular coordinate, located one above the other with some non-working gap δ_{nw} and relative to each other mirror-like, movable E-shaped magnetic core consisting of a vertical rod 3 coinciding with the vertical axis of the crescent-shaped open rings, and three parallel radially arranged rods 4,5,6, in the air gaps between the extreme pairs 4 and 5, 5 and 6, in which parts of the corresponding crescent-shaped open rings 1 or 2 enter. The bases of the E-shaped magnetic core – rod 3 freely cover the series-counter-connected sections 7, 8 of the excitation winding and series-counter-connected sections 9, 10 of the measuring winding. On the upper and lower end parts of the rod 3 of the movable E-shaped magnetic chain, the semi-axes 11 and 12 are rigidly fastened, which are mechanically connected to the controlled object (Fig. 1 is not shown).

The transformer converter of angular displacements works as follows.

The excitation winding of the converter is powered by a sinusoidal current source. The sinusoidal current passing through the sections of the excitation winding creates working magnetic fluxes $Q_{\mu 1}$ and $Q_{\mu 2}$, which in the corresponding sections of the measuring winding, according to the law of electromagnetic induction, induce the corresponding EMF.

Fig.1. Design diagram of the new sensor transformer converter of angular displacements: 1,2 – fixed crescent-shaped open rings; 3 - movable E-shaped magnetic chain; 4-6 - parallel radially spaced rods; 7,8 - series-counter-connected sections of the excitation winding; 9,10 - series-counter-connected sections of the measuring winding; 11,12 - mechanically rigidly connected with a controlled semi-axis object.

The magnetic capacities of the working air gaps (δ_p) between the movable radial rods 4,5 and the fixed crescent-shaped open ring 1, as well as between the movable radial rods 5,6 and the fixed crescent-shaped open ring 2 are defined as [7]:

$$C_{\mu\delta_p1} = \frac{\mu_0 S_{\mu\delta_p1}(\alpha)}{2\delta_p}, \quad (1) \quad C_{\mu\delta_p2} = \frac{\mu_0 S_{\mu\delta_p2}(\alpha)}{2\delta_p}, \quad (2)$$

where $\mu_0 = 4\pi \cdot 10^{-7} [H \cdot m^{-1}]$ is magnetic constant; $S_{\mu\delta_p1}(\alpha) = \frac{ba}{\pi}(\alpha_m + \alpha)$, $S_{\mu\delta_p2}(\alpha) = \frac{ba}{\pi}(\alpha_m - \alpha)$ are the active areas of the sector of fixed crescent-shaped unclosed rings 1 and 2, overlapped by movable radial rods 5-6; b is the width of three parallel radially arranged rods 4, 5, 6; a is the maximum width of each crescent-shaped unclosed ring, equal to twice the value of the step a of the Archimedean spiral; α , α_m are the angular displacement of the movable magnetic core and its maximum value.

The working magnetic fluxes $Q_{\mu1}$ and $Q_{\mu2}$ are defined as (without taking into account the magnetic resistance of the steel part, scattering fluxes, buckling at the ends and in the area of the moving part of the magnetic chain) [8]:

$$Q_{\mu1} = F_e \frac{\mu_0 S_{\mu\delta_p1}(\alpha)}{2\delta_p}, \quad (3) \quad Q_{\mu2} = F_e \frac{\mu_0 S_{\mu\delta_p2}(\alpha)}{2\delta_p}, \quad (4)$$

where $F_e = I_e w_e$ is magnetomotive force of the excitation winding section created by the current I_e .

The EMF induced by the working magnetic fluxes in the sections of the measuring winding 9 and 10 are defined as:

$$\dot{E}_9 = -j\omega \dot{I}_e w_e w_{out} \frac{\mu_0 S_{\mu\delta_p1}(\alpha)}{2\delta_p}, \quad (5) \quad \dot{E}_{10} = -j\omega \dot{I}_e w_e w_{out} \frac{\mu_0 S_{\mu\delta_p2}(\alpha)}{2\delta_p}, \quad (6)$$

into account. This circumstance to some extent reduces the accuracy of determining the analytical equation of the static characteristic of the new angular displacement converter.

We will consider the following three cases of calculating the distribution of linear magnetic chain parameters in this work:

1) the linear values of the magnetic resistance of the radial jumpers and the magnetic capacitance of the working air gap (δ_p) between the radial jumper and the active part of the crescent-shaped open ring are different from zero and their values along the length of the radial jumpers are constant, i.e. $Z_{\mu\pi} = const$ and $C_{\mu\pi\pi} = const$, and the magnetic capacitance of the air gap (assuming that $\delta_s \gg \delta_p$) between adjacent radial jumpers is zero, i.e. $C_{\mu_s} = 0$;

2) the linear values of the magnetic resistance of the radial jumpers and the magnetic capacitance between adjacent radial jumpers are different from zero and their values along the length of the radial jumpers are constant, i.e. $Z_{\mu\pi} = const$ and $C_{\mu\pi\pi} = const$, and the magnetic capacitance of the working air gap between the radial jumper and the active part of the crescent-shaped open ring ($C_{\mu p}$) is considered as a concentrated parameter of the magnetic chains;

3) the linear values of the magnetic resistance of the radial jumpers and the magnetic capacitance between adjacent radial jumpers, as well as the magnetic capacitance of the working air gap between the radial jumper and the active part of the crescent-shaped open ring ($C_{\mu p}$) are different from zero and their values along the length of the radial jumpers are constant, i.e. $Z_{\mu\pi} = const$, $C_{\mu\pi\pi} = const$ and $C_{\mu p\pi} = const$.

In all cases of the analysis of magnetic chains, the nonlinearity of the characteristics of the magnetic resistance of the magnetic chainsteel part, the buckling flows at the ends of the chain and in the area of the movable ferromagnetic core, as well as the longitudinal dimensions of the excitation winding are neglected. These assumptions, as shown in [3], do not introduce significant inaccuracies, but significantly simplify the analysis of the researched magnetic chain.

1. The constructive scheme of the researched linear magnetic chain and the replacement scheme of its elementary section for the first case of calculating the distribution of parameters are shown in Figure3. In the calculations, the magnetic chain is represented in the form of a n-shaped magnetic core, a ferromagnetic core is freely placed between parallel long rods with some gaps δ_p , the width of which varies linearly along the length of the long rods depending on the value and direction of the rotation angle of the corresponding crescent-shaped open ring, i.e. $2x = \frac{a}{\pi}(\alpha_m \pm \alpha)$ (when the rotation angle α of the radial jumpers 4-6 changes from $-\alpha_m$ to α_m , x changes within: $0 \leq x \leq X_m$).

So make the following equations based on Kirchhoff's laws for an elementary section of the length dx_1 of the magnetic chain (Fig.3) [3]:

$$Q'_{\mu x_1} = -U_{\mu x_1} C_{\mu p\pi}, \quad (8) \qquad U'_{\mu x_1} = -2Z_{\mu\pi} Q_{\mu x_1}, \quad (9)$$

where $Q_{\mu x_1}$, [Wb] and $U_{\mu x_1}$, [A] are respectively, the magnetic flux in parallel long rods and the magnetic voltage between the long rod and the ferromagnetic core; $Z_{\mu 0} = \frac{\delta_s}{\mu\mu_0bh}$ is - magnetic resistance of the base of the n-shaped magnetic core, [H^{-1}];

Fig.3. The constructive scheme of the linear magnetic chain under study (a) and the replacement scheme of its elementary section (b) for the first case of taking into account the distribution of parameters.

$Z_{\mu\pi} = \frac{1}{\mu\mu_0bh}$, $[H^{-1} \cdot m^{-1}]$ and $C_{\mu\pi\pi} = \mu_0 \frac{b}{2\delta_p}$, $[H \cdot m^{-1}]$ are linear values, respectively, of the magnetic resistance of the long rods and the magnetic capacitance of the air gaps δ_p between the long rod and the ferromagnetic core, per unit length of the rods; $\mu = const$ and $\mu_0 = 4\pi \cdot 10^{-7} [H \cdot m^{-1}]$ are, respectively, the relative magnetic permeability of the magnetic core material and the magnetic constant (absolute magnetic permeability of air); x , X_M are the width of the movable ferromagnetic core along the length of the long rods of the n-shaped magnetic core and its maximum value, $[m]$. The geometric dimensions are shown in Fig. 3, a. It should be noted that the magnetic resistance of the ferromagnetic core is assumed to be zero.

Differentiating equation (8) and substituting (9) into it, we obtain the following homogeneous second-order differential equation with constant coefficients:

$$Q''_{\mu x_1} = 2Z_{\mu\pi}C_{\mu\pi\pi}Q_{\mu x_1}. \quad (10)$$

The general solution of the differential equation (10), as is known [8], has the following form:

$$Q_{\mu x_1} = A_1 e^{\gamma_p x_1} + A_2 e^{-\gamma_p x_1}, \quad (11)$$

where A_1 and A_2 are constant integrations, $[Wb]$; $\gamma_p = \sqrt{2Z_{\mu\pi}C_{\mu\pi\pi}}$, $[m^{-1}]$ is the velocity of propagation of the magnetic field in a $2x$ -long magnetic chain.

From equation (8), taking into account (11) for the magnetic voltage, we obtain the following equation:

$$U_{\mu x_1} = -A_1 \frac{\gamma_p}{C_{\mu\pi\pi}} e^{\gamma_p x_1} + A_2 \frac{\gamma_p}{C_{\mu\pi\pi}} e^{-\gamma_p x_1}, \quad (12)$$

The values of A_1 and A_2 are based on the following boundary conditions:

$$U_{\mu x_1=0} = F_e - Q_{\mu x_1=0} [Z_{\mu 0} + 2Z_{\mu\pi}(X_M - x)], \quad (13) \quad Q_{\mu x_1=2x} = 0, \quad (14)$$

where $Z_{\mu 0} = \frac{\delta_s}{\mu\mu_0bh}$, $[H^{-1}]$ is the magnetic resistance of the base of the n-shaped magnetic core.

Substituting the boundary values $Q_{\mu x_1}$ and $U_{\mu x_1}$ into the corresponding equations (13) and (14) and solving the resulting system of algebraic equations with respect to the unknowns A_1 and A_2 , we find their following values:

$$A_1 = -\frac{F_e}{2\Delta_1} e^{-2\gamma_p x}, \quad (15) \quad A_2 = \frac{F_e}{2\Delta_1} e^{2\gamma_p x}, \quad (16)$$

where $\Delta_1 = [Z_{\mu 0} + 2Z_{\mu\pi}(X_M - x)]sh(2\gamma_p x) + \frac{\gamma_p}{C_{\mu\pi\pi}} ch(2\gamma_p x)$, $[H^{-1}]$.

Substituting the found values A_1 and A_2 into equations (11) and (12), we obtain the following:

$$Q_{\mu x_1} = \frac{F_e}{2\Delta_1} sh[\gamma_p(2x - x_1)], \quad (17)$$

$$U_{\mu x_1} = -\frac{F_e}{2\gamma_p\Delta_1} ch[\gamma_p(2x - x_1)]. \quad (18)$$

The value of the magnetic flux, under the influence of which EMF is induced in the measuring winding, is from (17) find as:

$$Q_{\mu x} = Q_{\mu x_1=0} = \frac{F_e}{2\Delta_1} sh(2\gamma_p x). \quad (19)$$

2. The constructive scheme of the linear magnetic chain under study and the substitution scheme of the elementary section for the second case of calculating the distribution of parameters are shown in Fig.4.

Let's make the following equations based on Kirchhoff's laws for an elementary section of the length dx_1 of the magnetic chain located on the left side of the ferromagnetic core (Fig.4):

$$Q'_{\mu x_1} = -U_{\mu x_1} C_{\mu s \Pi}, \quad (20) \quad U'_{\mu x_1} = -2Z_{\mu \Pi} Q_{\mu x_1}, \quad (21)$$

where $C_{\mu s \Pi} = \mu_0 \frac{b}{\delta_s}$, [$H \cdot m^{-1}$] is the linear value of the magnetic capacitance of the air gap δ_s between the long rods of the n-shaped magnetic core, per unit length of the rods.

The general solution of differential equations (20) and (21) has the following form:

$$Q_{\mu x_1} = A_1 e^{\gamma_s x_1} + A_2 e^{-\gamma_s x_1}, \quad (22)$$

$$U_{\mu x_1} = A_1 \frac{\gamma_s}{C_{\mu p \Pi}} e^{\gamma_s x_1} - A_2 \frac{\gamma_s}{C_{\mu p \Pi}} e^{-\gamma_s x_1}, \quad (23)$$

where $\gamma_s = \sqrt{2Z_{\mu \Pi} C_{\mu s \Pi}}$, [m^{-1}].

The differential equations type and their solution for the part of the magnetic chain to the right of the ferromagnetic core will be the same as for equations (8), (9) and (11), (12). Here we will limit ourselves to giving the following general solutions:

$$Q_{\mu x_2} = A_3 e^{\gamma_s x_2} + A_4 e^{-\gamma_s x_2}, \quad (24)$$

$$U_{\mu x_2} = -A_3 \frac{\gamma_s}{C_{\mu s \Pi}} e^{\gamma_s x_2} + A_4 \frac{\gamma_s}{C_{\mu s \Pi}} e^{-\gamma_s x_2}. \quad (25)$$

Fig.4. The constructive scheme of the magnetic chain (a) and the replacement scheme of its elementary section (b) for the second case of calculating the distribution of parameters

The following boundary conditions are valid for the magnetic chain under consideration:

$$U_{\mu x_1=X_M-x} = F_e - Q_{\mu x_1=X_M-x} Z_{\mu 0}, \quad (26) \quad Q_{\mu x_1=0} = Q_{\mu x_2=0} + U_{\mu x_2=0} C_{\mu p}, \quad (27)$$

$$U_{\mu x_1=0} = U_{\mu x_2=0}, \quad (28) \quad Q_{\mu x_2=X_M-x} = 0. \quad (29)$$

Substituting the boundary values of magnetic fluxes and magnetic stresses into the corresponding equations (26)-(29), we obtain the following algebraic equations:

$$\left(Z_{\mu 0} + \frac{\gamma_s}{C_{\mu s n}}\right) e^{\gamma_s(X_M - x)} A_1 + \left(Z_{\mu 0} - \frac{\gamma_s}{C_{\mu s n}}\right) e^{-\gamma_s(X_M - x)} A_2 = F_B, \quad (30)$$

$$A_1 + A_2 + \left(\frac{\gamma_s C_{\mu p}}{C_{\mu s n}} - 1\right) A_3 - \left(\frac{\gamma_s C_{\mu p}}{C_{\mu s n}} + 1\right) A_4 = 0, \quad (31)$$

$$A_1 - A_2 + A_3 - A_4 = 0, \quad (32)$$

$$e^{\gamma_s(X_M - x)} A_3 + e^{-\gamma_s(X_M - x)} A_4 = 0. \quad (33)$$

Solving together equations (30)-(33) with respect to $A_1 \div A_4$, we find their following values:

$$A_1 = \frac{F_e e^{\gamma_s(X_M - x)}}{\Delta_2} + \frac{\gamma_s F_e C_{\mu p} e^{\gamma_s(X_M - x)}}{2 C_{\mu s n} \Delta_2} + \frac{\gamma_s F_e C_{\mu p} e^{-\gamma_s(X_M - x)}}{2 C_{\mu s n} \Delta_2}, \quad (34)$$

$$A_2 = -\frac{F_e e^{-\gamma_s(X_M - x)}}{\Delta_2} + \frac{\gamma_s F_e C_{\mu p} e^{\gamma_s(X_M - x)}}{2 C_{\mu s n} \Delta_2} + \frac{\gamma_s F_e C_{\mu p} e^{-\gamma_s(X_M - x)}}{2 C_{\mu s n} \Delta_2}, \quad (35)$$

$$A_3 = -\frac{F_e e^{-\gamma_s(X_M - x)}}{\Delta_2}, \quad (36) \quad A_4 = \frac{F_e e^{\gamma_s(X_M - x)}}{\Delta_2}, \quad (37)$$

where:
$$\Delta_2 = \frac{Z_{\mu 0} \gamma_s C_{\mu p}}{C_{\mu s n}} + sh[2\gamma_s(X_M - x)] \left[2Z_{\mu 0} + \left(\frac{\gamma_s}{C_{\mu s n}}\right)^2 C_{\mu p} \right] + ch[2\gamma_s(X_M - x)] \cdot \frac{\gamma_s}{C_{\mu s n}} (Z_{\mu 0} C_{\mu p} + 2), [H^{-1}].$$

Substituting the found values $A_1 \div A_4$ into equations (22)-(25), we obtain the following expressions for magnetic fluxes and magnetic stresses:

$$Q_{\mu x_1} = \frac{2F_e}{\Delta_2} sh[\gamma_s(X_M - x + x_1)] + \frac{2\gamma_s F_e C_{\mu p}}{C_{\mu s n} \Delta_2} ch[\gamma_s(X_M - x)] ch(\gamma_s x_1), \quad (38)$$

$$U_{\mu x_1} = \frac{2\gamma_s F_e}{C_{\mu s n} \Delta_2} ch[\gamma_s(X_M - x + x_1)] + \frac{2\gamma_s^2 F_e C_{\mu p}}{C_{\mu s n}^2 \Delta_2} ch[\gamma_s(X_M - x)] sh(\gamma_s x_1), \quad (39)$$

$$Q_{\mu x_2} = \frac{2F_e}{\Delta_2} sh[\gamma_s(X_M - x - x_2)], \quad (40)$$

$$U_{\mu x_2} = \frac{2\gamma_s F_e}{C_{\mu s n} \Delta_2} ch[\gamma_s(X_M - x - x_2)], \quad (41)$$

The value of the magnetic flux, under the influence of which EMF is induced in the measuring winding of the converter, is from (22) as:

$$Q_{\mu x} = Q_{\mu x_1 = X_M - x} = \frac{2F_e}{\Delta_2} sh[2\gamma_s(X_M - x)] + \frac{2\gamma_s F_e C_{\mu p}}{C_{\mu s n} \Delta_2} ch^2[\gamma_s(X_M - x)], \quad (41)$$

3. The constructive scheme of the researched linear magnetic chain for the third case of taking into account the distribution of parameters is shown in Fig.5.

The general solution of the differential equations compiled for the first (with variable x_1) and second (x_2) sections of the magnetic chain will be in the form similar to equations (22)-(25), and for the third section – equations (11) and (12), i.e.:

$$Q_{\mu x_1} = A_1 e^{\gamma_s x_1} + B_1 e^{-\gamma_s x_1}, \quad (42)$$

$$U_{\mu x_1} = A_1 \frac{\gamma_s}{C_{\mu p n}} e^{\gamma_s x_1} - B_1 \frac{\gamma_s}{C_{\mu p n}} e^{-\gamma_s x_1}, \quad (43)$$

$$Q_{\mu x_2} = A_2 e^{\gamma_s x_2} + B_2 e^{-\gamma_s x_2}, \quad (44)$$

$$U_{\mu x_2} = -A_2 \frac{\gamma_s}{C_{\mu s n}} e^{\gamma_s x_2} + B_2 \frac{\gamma_s}{C_{\mu s n}} e^{-\gamma_s x_2}. \quad (45)$$

$$B_2 = \frac{4F_e\gamma_p\gamma_s}{C_{\mu p\pi}C_{\mu s\pi}\Delta_3} \{ch[\gamma_s(X_M - x)] + sh[\gamma_s(X_M - x)]\}, \quad (61)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_3 = & \frac{8}{C_{\mu s\pi}^2 C_{\mu p\pi}^2} \{2\gamma_s^2\gamma_p C_{\mu s\pi} C_{\mu p\pi} ch^2[\gamma_s(X_M - x)]ch(2\gamma_p x) - \\ & -\gamma_s^2\gamma_p C_{\mu s\pi} C_{\mu p\pi} ch(2\gamma_p x) + \gamma_s\gamma_p^2 C_{\mu s\pi}^2 ch[\gamma_s(X_M - x)]sh[\gamma_s(X_M - x)]sh(2\gamma_p x) + \\ & + 2Z_{\mu 0}\gamma_s\gamma_p C_{\mu s\pi}^2 C_{\mu p\pi} ch[\gamma_s(X_M - x)]sh[\gamma_s(X_M - x)]ch(2\gamma_p x) + \\ & + Z_{\mu 0}\gamma_p^2 C_{\mu s\pi}^3 sh(2\gamma_p x)ch^2[\gamma_s(X_M - x)] - Z_{\mu 0}\gamma_p^2 C_{\mu s\pi}^3 sh(2\gamma_p x) + \\ & + Z_{\mu 0}\gamma_s^2 C_{\mu s\pi} C_{\mu p\pi}^2 ch^2[\gamma_s(X_M - x)]sh(2\gamma_p x) + \\ & + \gamma_s^3 C_{\mu p\pi}^2 ch[\gamma_s(X_M - x)]sh[\gamma_s(X_M - x)]sh(2\gamma_p x)\}, [H^{-3} \cdot m^{-1}]. \end{aligned}$$

Substituting the found values $A_1 \div A_3$ and $B_1 \div B_3$ into equations (42)-(45), we obtain the following expressions for magnetic fluxes and magnetic stresses:

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{\mu x_1} = & \frac{8F_e}{C_{\mu s\pi}^2 C_{\mu p\pi}^2 \Delta_3} \{\gamma_s^2 C_{\mu p\pi}^2 ch[\gamma_s(X_M - x)]sh(2\gamma_p x)ch(\gamma_s x_1) + \\ & + \gamma_p^2 C_{\mu s\pi}^2 sh[\gamma_s(X_M - x)]sh(\gamma_p x)sh(\gamma_s x_1) + \\ & + \gamma_p\gamma_s C_{\mu p\pi} C_{\mu s\pi} ch[\gamma_s(X_M - x)]ch(2\gamma_p x)sh(\gamma_s x_1) + \\ & + \gamma_p\gamma_s C_{\mu p\pi} C_{\mu s\pi} sh[\gamma_s(X_M - x)]ch(2\gamma_p x)ch(\gamma_s x_1)\}, \quad (62) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} U_{\mu x_1} = & \frac{8F_e\gamma_s}{C_{\mu s\pi}^3 C_{\mu p\pi}^2 \Delta_3} \{\gamma_s^2 C_{\mu p\pi}^2 ch[\gamma_s(X_M - x)]sh(2\gamma_p x)sh(\gamma_s x_1) + \\ & + \gamma_p^2 C_{\mu s\pi}^2 sh[\gamma_s(X_M - x)]sh(2\gamma_p x)ch(\gamma_s x_1) + \\ & + \gamma_p\gamma_s C_{\mu p\pi} C_{\mu s\pi} ch[\gamma_s(X_M - x)]ch(2\gamma_p x)ch(\gamma_s x_1) + \\ & + \gamma_p\gamma_s C_{\mu p\pi} C_{\mu s\pi} sh[\gamma_s(X_M - x)]ch(2\gamma_p x)sh(\gamma_s x_1)\}, \quad (63) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{\mu x_3} = & -\frac{8F_e\gamma_s}{C_{\mu s\pi}^2 C_{\mu p\pi} \Delta_3} \{\gamma_s C_{\mu p\pi} ch[\gamma_s(X_M - x)]ch(2\gamma_p x)sh(\gamma_p x_3) - \\ & -\gamma_p C_{\mu s\pi} sh[\gamma_s(X_M - x)]ch(2\gamma_p x)ch(\gamma_p x_3) - \\ & -\gamma_s C_{\mu p\pi} ch[\gamma_s(X_M - x)]sh(2\gamma_p x)ch(\gamma_p x_3) + \\ & + \gamma_p C_{\mu s\pi} sh[\gamma_s(X_M - x)]sh(2\gamma_p x)sh(\gamma_p x_3)\}, \quad (64) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} U_{\mu x_3} = & \frac{8F_e\gamma_s\gamma_p}{C_{\mu s\pi}^2 C_{\mu p\pi}^2 \Delta_3} \{\gamma_s C_{\mu p\pi} ch[\gamma_s(X_M - x)]ch(2\gamma_p x)ch(\gamma_p x_3) - \\ & -\gamma_p C_{\mu s\pi} sh[\gamma_s(X_M - x)]ch(2\gamma_p x)sh(\gamma_p x_3) - \\ & -\gamma_s C_{\mu p\pi} ch[\gamma_s(X_M - x)]sh(2\gamma_p x)sh(\gamma_p x_3) + \\ & + \gamma_p C_{\mu s\pi} sh[\gamma_s(X_M - x)]sh(2\gamma_p x)ch(\gamma_p x_3)\}, \quad (65) \end{aligned}$$

$$Q_{\mu x_2} = \frac{8F_e\gamma_p\gamma_s}{C_{\mu p\pi} C_{\mu s\pi} \Delta_3} \{sh[\gamma_s(X_M - x)]ch(\gamma_s x_2) - ch[\gamma_s(X_M - x)]sh(\gamma_s x_2)\}, \quad (66)$$

$$U_{\mu x_2} = \frac{8F_e\gamma_p^2\gamma_s}{C_{\mu s\pi}^2 C_{\mu p\pi} \Delta_3} \{ch[\gamma_s(X_M - x)]ch(\gamma_s x_2) - sh[\gamma_s(X_M - x)]sh(\gamma_s x_2)\}, \quad (67)$$

The value of the magnetic flux, under the influence of which EMF is induced in the measuring winding of the converter, is from (62) as:

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{\mu x} = Q_{\mu x_1=x_M-x} = & \frac{8F_e}{C_{\mu s\pi}^2 C_{\mu p\pi}^2 \Delta_3} \{\gamma_s^2 C_{\mu p\pi}^2 ch^2[\gamma_s(X_M - x)]sh(2\gamma_p x) + \\ & + \gamma_p^2 C_{\mu s\pi}^2 sh^2[\gamma_s(X_M - x)]sh(\gamma_p x) + \\ & + \gamma_p\gamma_s C_{\mu p\pi} C_{\mu s\pi} sh[2\gamma_s(X_M - x)]ch(2\gamma_p x)\}, \quad (68) \end{aligned}$$

Expressions (3), (4), (17)-(19), (38)-(41) and (62)-(68) are magnetic chainmathematical models of new differential type angular displacement transformer converter for various degrees of accounting for the distribution of magnetic resistance and magnetic capacitance parameters, which can be used in the main characteristics research and design of the converter in question.

Conclusion. So, the article develops magnetic chainmathematical models of new differential type angular displacement transformer converter with a variable active area of the movable core, in which the width of the movable ferromagnetic core is a function of the angular displacement of the converter.

In this case, the magnetic chain of the converter, divided into three characteristic sections (before the mobile ferromagnetic core, ferromagnetic core and after the ferromagnetic core), is considered as a magnetic chain with distributed parameters.

It is established that when the magnetic resistance of the magnetic chainsteel part is not taken into account, the working magnetic flux is a linear function of the movable ferromagnetic core angular displacement of the converter.

The obtained mathematical models of the transformer converter magnetic chain of angular displacements in the form of analytical expressions of the magnetic flux in long ferromagnetic rods and the magnetic voltage between them for three characteristic sections allow to take into account the distribution of the magnetic resistance parameters of long ferromagnetic rods and the magnetic capacity of the air gap between them, as well as the magnetic capacity of the air gap between the rods and the movable ferromagnetic core.

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